

MILD STEEL CORROSION INHIBITION IN ACIDIC WATER ENVIRONMENTS WITH SODIUM NITRATE: AN UP-TO-DATE RESEARCH PROGRESS REVIEW REPORT

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Abstract

Corrosion inhibitors are effective alternatives for protecting steel from corrosion in aqueous environments. Synthetic corrosion inhibitors pose serious global environmental issues and health risks; nevertheless, a few of them have excellent environmental properties, handling safety, and very high corrosion inhibition efficiencies. This study presents an up-to-date literature review on sodium nitrate as an inorganic synthetic corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in acidic water environments, showcasing its general uses, properties, safety level, availability level, cost, and research advances as integrated knowledge for research gaps and progress on its corrosion inhibition studies. The review shows that mild steel is the topmost structural metal for engineering systems due to its greater versatility in terms of outstanding strength, fabrication properties, affordability, widespread use, and sustainable availability around the world, but it has very low corrosion resistance. It contributes to approximately 90% of all steel types and 90% of all corrosion problems worldwide. Acidic water environments are highly aggressive and capable of rapidly corroding mild steel electrochemically, leading to its significant weight loss, structural integrity reduction, and failure possibility with unpredictable hazardous consequences. The review also shows that corrosion inhibition efficiency of mild steel with sodium nitrate can vary greatly depending on the corrosivity extent of the environment. Sodium nitrate best inhibits mild steel corrosion in industrial environments at optimized concentrations ranging from 75 mg/L to over 1000 mg/L. The corrosion inhibition of mild steel with sodium nitrate is mostly focused on neutral-to-alkaline and oxygenated water environments, such as simulated cooling waters, concrete pore solutions, and industrial cleaning solutions, but is greatly unresearched in several natural acidic waters, including sour waters; highly saline, especially chloride, waters; and high-flow-velocity waters at ambient and higher temperatures.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is any natural process, particularly an electrochemical process that gradually and insidiously attacks a material component, especially metal, through interaction with its surroundings, resulting in the reduction or destruction of its useful properties and values [1, 2]. All engineering materials can corrode under various macro- and micro-environmental conditions, but critical structural materials, such as steel, concrete, wood, and aluminum, are particularly vulnerable to severe corrosion and failures during applications. Steel is the most adaptable structural metal and is utilized in a variety of applications due to its exceptional engineering qualities, greater availability at comparatively lower prices, and sustainable production for many more years. The corrosion resistance of steel decreases as its carbon content or alloy elements decreases. Mild steel contains negligible alloy elements and the lowest carbon content, only up to 0.3%. Approximately 90% of all steels used for engineering systems are mild steel, and its use in various engineering applications accounts for 90% of corrosion problems worldwide [2, 3, 4]. Mild steel is used in all areas of engineering technology, from mere household and farm parts to large industrial structures, such as road bridges, automobiles, railways, aircraft, storage tanks, and ocean liners, due to its unsurpassable fabrication properties, such as forgeability, formability, bendability, braze-ability, weldability, and machinability, coupled with its easy accessibility, affordable rates, sustainable production in the foreseeable future, good hardness, high-tensile, high-impact, and excellent fatigue strengths that are maintained without breaking for a very long time [1, 3, 4]. Therefore, corrosion of mild steel is a significant industrial issue, causing enormous economic losses and structural failures, sometimes with hazardous consequences [1-6]. Acidic environments or high-moisture conditions have a severe impact on the corrosion of mild steel. Acidic conditions lead to high, uniform corrosion rates of steel due to their ability to dissolve the protective iron oxide films on the metal's surface. Mild steel is more commonly exposed to acidic water environments than other aqueous water environments, and the acidic water environments it is exposed to include natural waters from various locations, artificial waters, and water conditions created by unavoidable natural or artificial circumstances. For example, steel systems are exposed to strong acid solutions such as HCl injected into oil wells to dissolve carbonate rocks and improve flow, producing sour, sweet waters that create acidic conditions and high corrosion rates; petroleum that becomes acidic and contacts steel components of heat exchangers and pipes in refineries; HCl and H₂SO₄ in the form of tanks during industrial processing and maintenance, such as pickling and descaling; chemical cleaning of industrial heat exchangers, boilers, and reactors using acids that can damage the steel if not managed; fertilizers, especially phosphoric acid, in the form of pipelines; and local acidic pockets in marine environments naturally created by pollutions to acidic groundwater and soils, particularly in marshy or mining areas [1-6]. HCl

Various techniques are used to control steel corrosion in a variety of environmental circumstances, and a lot of money, to the tune of several billion American dollars, is spent annually globally on research on better techniques of controlling mild steel corrosion in various aqueous environment types, but the up-to-date costs and technological sophistication on the subject are still far from ideal achievements [2-8]. The use of corrosion inhibitors is one of the most versatile, economical, and widely used techniques in aqueous environments. A corrosion inhibitor is any substance that can restrain corrosion of a material component or system to at most 100% in an aqueous environment when added in small quantities to the environment, depending on its effectiveness level on the material in the environment [2-8]. There are various corrosion inhibitor types that can be employed for mild steel, but in specific environments, the inhibitors used must be effective, cost-effective, available, dependable, and eco-friendly. Other parameters, such as environmental limitations and the concentration and duration for which the inhibitor is most effective for the steel and environment, must be established before employing them. Heterocyclic corrosion inhibitors containing polar groups and π -electrons, as well as organic

products with one or more polar functionalities are so far the best types of corrosion inhibitors for steel, aluminum, and some other metal types. This is due to their ability to easily displace water molecules and get adsorbed and bonded on the metal surface, with the bonding efficiency enhanced by the presence of polar functions with S, O, or N atoms in the molecule, heterocyclic compounds, and π -electrons, so they act as a tight barrier layer and prevent or reduce the ingress of corrosive agents or species [2-4]. Many plant extracts have been under research as alternatives for synthetic corrosion inhibitors of mild steel in various aqueous environments due to their excellent environmental properties, handling safety, and availability, sustainability, and corrosion inhibition capabilities. However, a number of synthetic organic and inorganic corrosion inhibitors also meet those characteristics with even more effective inhibition efficiencies than plant extracts. Sodium nitrate is an inorganic anodic corrosion inhibitor of carbon steel in aqueous environments. It is typically used to form protective passive films and reduce carbon steel corrosion rates in acidic or saline environments. It performs best at optimized concentrations, with numerous studies indicating its optimal corrosion inhibition of mild steel at concentrations ranging from 75 mg/L to over 1000 mg/ in various aqueous environments [2, 3, 9]. The aim of this paper is to present basic information on the use of sodium nitrate as a significant inorganic corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in acidic water environments, highlighting its widespread availability, low cost, very high safety level to the environment and personnel, areas of applications, areas of research need, and current research findings to reveal research gaps and progress in usage as a corrosion inhibitor.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The available literature on sodium nitrate with respect to its physical and chemical properties, industrial uses, potential health risks to employees, production, availability, and cost-effectiveness, highlighting its strengths and weaknesses as a corrosion inhibitor of mild steel in acidic aqueous environments, was collected from reputable journals, theses, books, books of conference proceedings, business websites, etc. on the Internet, and institutional libraries. The sourced information was integrated and fine-tuned, and areas where the use of sodium nitrate and its research for corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic aqueous environments need to be addressed were revealed for further research to consolidate its inhibition data for better application.

2.1 Types and characteristics of typical inhibitors used to protect mild steel from corrosion in acidic water environments

The key types of corrosion inhibitors for mild steel in acidic water are as follows [2, 9-16]:

- i. Green/Natural Inhibitors are essentially plant extracts or natural compounds. Some plant extracts, such as those from Viola, rice straw, and citrus peels, are highly effective because of their complex organic molecules, often achieving high inhibition efficiencies of over 90%. Natural compounds, such as gum Arabic, provide good inhibition, which increases with their concentration in corrosive media.
- ii. Organic/Synthetic Inhibitors, which are essentially triazoles and thiazoles such as 2-amino-4-phenylthiazole and 3-(4-ethyl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-1-phenylpropanone, show high efficiency, especially in HCl; thioamides and tyrimidines such as 2-methyl-1,3-thiazole-4-carbothioamide derivatives; polyethylene glycol (PEG), an efficient, synthetic polymer inhibitor that performs better than some natural gums, thiols, amides, carboxylic acids, and imidazole derivatives; and halides, often used in combination with other inhibitors to boost effectiveness. The inhibition mechanism and performance of these inhibitors typically follow adsorption isotherms such as Langmuir or Frumkin, forming a protective barrier that replaces adsorbed species. Although their inhibition efficiency can decrease at high temperatures, many inhibitors still show good performance, with inhibition efficiencies of over 90%–95%, as observed with specific plant extracts, thiazoles, and triazoles.

2.2 Sources of acidic water

Acidic water environments are those with a pH of less than or equal to 6.5. These environmental types constitute the bulk of the most aggressive environments to which mild steel is commonly exposed. Acidic water environments occur at the micro and macro levels and include the following [17-19]:

- i. Acid rain, created when atmospheric water vapor reacts with pollutants like CO₂, SO_x and NO_x gases, forming acids that fall as rain.
- ii. Mining activities result in the drainage of mines and exposure of sulfur-containing minerals, such as pyrite, to air and water, thereby creating sulfuric acid.
- iii. Acidification of certain areas of the sea or fresh water by natural processes such as carbon dioxide absorption and decomposition of some plants, animals, fish, and reptiles. as organic matter, and pollution from acidic sources such as volcanic eruptions.
- iv. Natural decomposition by soil microbes and decaying plant material in wetlands/swamps that release organic acids.
- v. Industrial pollution by chemical manufacturing, wastewater, runoff, and emissions from coal-powered power plants, which significantly reduce water pH
- vi. The geological nature of groundwater passing through some areas, such as igneous rock, granite, or low-carbonate soil, which naturally causes it to become acidic.
- vii. Rain naturally absorbing CO₂ from the air, creating weak carbonic acid.

2.3 Sodium nitrate

Sodium nitrate is also known as Chile saltpeter. It is a highly water-soluble inorganic chemical compound with the formula NaNO₃, molar mass of 84.9947 g/mol and a density of 2.257 g/cm³. It is white, odorless, and crystal or granular [20, 21]. Fig. 1 shows the high-purity sodium nitrate sample.

Fig. 1. Image of high-purity sodium nitrate sample [17, 18].

2.3.1 Production and availability levels

Sodium nitrate is produced in two ways: by mining natural deposits at some locations around the world and by neutralizing nitric acid (HNO₃) with sodium-based bases such as sodium hydroxide (NaOH), sodium carbonate (Na₂CO₃), and sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO₃). At least 68% of it is produced industrially, while mining produces the rest. Its global annual production rate exceeds 5 million metric tons, with China, Chile, India, and the United States as the leading producers. Sodium nitrate is cheaply available in most countries, including Nigeria. Enx Energy and Chemicals Nigeria Limited is its leading supplier in Nigeria. The average current global price of high-purity laboratory-grade sodium nitrate is estimated to be 71 USD per kilogram. A 2.5-kg bag of sodium nitrate, a

specialized reagent grade, costs about 100,000 Naira in Nigeria, and highly refined laboratory samples of 0.5 kg are also available in the country at 80 naira per sample [20, 21].

2.3.4 Applications

Sodium nitrate is primarily used as an agricultural fertilizer and food preservative (E251) in cured meats; however, it has many applications in enamel, glass, dyes, metallurgy, and other industries [20, 21, 22]. For example, it can be used as [20, 21, 22]:

- i. Flux, an oxidant in the enamel industry and preparation of raw materials for tantalum powder.
- ii. A decolorizer, defoamer, clarifier, and oxidizing flux for various glass types in the glass industry.
- iii. Quick-acting fertilizer for acidic soils, especially for fern root crops, such as beets and radishes, in the fertilizer industry
- iv. A raw material for producing picric acid and dyes in the dye industry.
- v. Heat treatment agent for steelmaking and aluminum alloy in the metallurgical industry
- vi. A metal cleaner and ferrous black bluing agent for the mechanical industry
- vii. A material in glassmaking, explosive production, and pyrotechnics.

Application as a corrosion inhibitor: sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) is used as an anodic corrosion inhibitor for mild steel, primarily in aqueous and concrete environments. It functions as a passivator, forming a protective, stable film of iron oxide (Fe_2O_3) or complexes on the metal surface [20, 21, 22]. It has applications as an inhibitor in the following areas [20, 21, 22]: Closed-loop cooling systems such as engine cooling systems and industrial cooling water are used to prevent corrosion, particularly in systems with high chloride concentrations.

- i. Concrete reinforcement in construction to prevent chloride-induced corrosion of steel rebar in mortar and concrete, especially when GGBS or fly ash is used.
- ii. Acidic media under specific conditions to inhibit carbon/mild steel corrosion in HCl solutions, with studies showing effectiveness at specific concentrations.
- iii. Surface treatment and metalworking as a component in paint formulations, coatings, and passivation baths to protect metallic components during manufacturing.
- iv. Simulated aqueous environments, where it is tested and used to inhibit corrosion in environments containing sulfate or chloride ions.

2.4.5 Issues

It is a widely used and highly effective corrosion inhibitor of carbon steel and aluminum alloys. It is suggested that it should be used at higher concentrations (1000 mmol of the environment) for better corrosion passivity because lower concentrations than this value below the critical or passivity threshold value may cause severe pitting and accelerate corrosion of the material to be protected. Its melting and boiling points are 308°C and 380°C , respectively. It is an oxidizer; therefore, it can intensify fires and is harmful if swallowed or inhaled, causing irritation. It is recommended to keep it away from flammable materials and combustible substances, and protective equipment (gloves, goggles) should be used to avoid skin/eye contact with it. Health organizations, such as the Center for Disease Control, advise that its daily intake be limited to 3.7 mg/kg of body weight. However, its frequent high intake in the human body is associated with a risk of developing diseases, such as type 1 diabetes, thyroid dysfunction, cardiovascular disease, and neurological issues, as well as colorectal, gastric, and pancreatic cancers, due to the formation of nitrosamines. In infants, its high intake can cause a serious blood disorder. Owing to its high-water solubility, it can cause contamination of groundwater and surface water, contribute to nutrient pollution, and affect aquatic ecosystems if overused in agricultural settings. Apart from these observations, sodium nitrate is generally an environmentally friendly corrosion inhibitor that is very safe to

personnel. It is also generally less toxic and more benign than the more commonly used sodium nitrite version [23, 24].

2.5.6 Corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic water environments

A review by Răuță et al. [25] examines recent advances in corrosion inhibitor technologies, focusing on sustainable and environmentally friendly solutions that address industrial efficiency and environmental safety. Corrosion is a ubiquitous problem that contributes to massive global economic losses, with costs estimated to be between 1% and 5% of GDP in different countries. Traditional inorganic corrosion inhibitors, while effective, are often based on toxic compounds, necessitating the development of more environmentally friendly and non-toxic alternatives. This study highlights innovative eco-friendly corrosion inhibitors derived from natural sources, including plant extracts and oils and biopolymers, as biodegradable substances that provide effective corrosion resistance with minimal environmental impact. In addition, this review explores organic-inorganic hybrid inhibitors and nanotechnology-enhanced coatings that demonstrate improved efficiency, durability, and adaptability across industries. Key considerations, such as application techniques, mechanisms of action, and the impact of environmental factors on inhibitor performance, are discussed. This comprehensive presentation contributes to the development of advanced corrosion inhibitors capable of meeting the requirements of modern industries while promoting sustainable and safe practices in corrosion management.

Pokorny et al. [26] contended that most of the worldwide sodium nitrate production is supplied from natural deposits in Chile and South America, and the rest is provided essentially as a by-product from nitric acid plants. Sodium nitrate is used as a fertilizer and in many industrial applications, primarily as an oxidizing agent. These include the manufacture of glass, explosives, and charcoal briquettes and the production of potassium compounds. Consumption of sodium nitrate for industrial uses has been rather steady, but its use as a fertilizer has declined. Various technical and industrial grades of sodium nitrate are available in addition to the agricultural grade. Surface mining methods are used to mine Chilean nitrate ore. The mineral recovery and processing procedures are described, as are the various purification steps. Sodium nitrate is synthetically produced by the absorption of waste nitrous oxide gases in an alkaline solution. Sodium nitrite (NaNO_2), is a versatile industrial chemical with applications that are widely based on its oxidizing properties or its ability to yield nitrous acid upon acidification. It is hygroscopic and quite soluble in water but not in most organic solvents. Sodium nitrite is a moderately strong oxidizer that is toxic by ingestion. It can react violently with some chemicals, evolve toxic NO_x on decomposition, and promote burning when exposed to fire. It may be derived from the reduction of sodium nitrate but is typically manufactured by the absorption of nitrogen oxides into solutions of sodium hydroxide or sodium carbonate. Dry and liquid forms of the product in several grades are offered in bulk and in a variety of packaging options. Dry products may be treated with an anti-cake agent. Typical assays include 99% NaNO_2 for dry products and 42% NaNO_2 for liquid products. The product is used in azo dyes, rubber chemicals, heat treating and heat-transfer salts, some meat curing, metal finishing, organic chemical syntheses, and as a corrosion inhibitor.

Medupin et al. [27] asserted that the integrity of mild steel affects its performance in many areas of modern manufacturing. However, corrosion remains an important concern with mild steel because it reverts the steel to its most stable oxide state. This has increased the search for sustainable alternatives to conventional inorganic corrosion inhibitors. Plant-based inhibitors are rapidly gaining attention among researchers due to their relative advantages. The sustainability perspective, which cuts across the economics, safety, and environmental impacts of plant-based inhibitors from plant-based extracts, must be considered to holistically address corrosion in mild steel. Furthermore, a clear understanding of the current trends in the deployment of environment-friendly inhibitors is necessary to operate in different environments. This study examines adsorption mechanisms and

characterization techniques, as well as several factors affecting the inhibition efficiency of plant-based corrosion inhibitors in relation to economic, safety, and environmental considerations. Additionally, it outlines a plan that allows for a structured reflection on the existing literature on corrosion control and management based on a sustainability perspective. Finally, although researchers have made a tremendous effort for corrosion inhibition in mild steel using other techniques, more research is still needed to develop sustainable technologies that could assist in isolating bioactive compounds responsible for inhibition, which could further minimize the incidence of wastage attributable to the inability to ascertain the exact amount of plant extracts for certain corrosion inhibition processes.

Adamu et al. [28] argued that inhibitors are regularly used as one of the principal techniques for preventing and controlling reinforcement corrosion. The effect of calcium nitrate and sodium nitrite inhibitors on the rebar corrosion of medium carbon steel in seawater and cassava fluid was investigated to determine the inhibitory potentials of the different inhibitors in the two media. Gravimetric and voltametric techniques were employed in this study, and 45 corrosion coupons of different dimensions were produced. Forty coupons were used for the gravimetric analysis and the remaining five for the corrosion potential measurements. Eight of the samples were used as controls, whereas the other eight samples were each admixed with calcium nitrate and sodium nitrite in concrete cubes. It was later immersed in seawater and cassava fluid for a total duration of 32 days, and the corrosion rates in mils per year were measured at an interval of 4 days. Two controls and admixed samples were immersed in seawater and cassava fluid, respectively, for 32 days to determine the corrosion potentials using a voltmeter and a Copper-Copper Sulfate Electrode (Cu/CuSO₄). The pH of each medium was measured throughout the exposure period. The results obtained expressed that all the samples except the control samples displayed some degree of inhibition. The inhibition levels of the admixed samples in seawater were higher than those in cassava fluid. Inhibition efficiencies for various inhibitors followed different trends in different environments. The inhibition efficiencies of calcium nitrate in cassava fluid and seawater were 26.81% and 64.85%, respectively. Inorganic inhibitors were effective in inhibiting corrosion in cyanide- and chloride-contaminated concrete cubes. Saura et al. [29] noted that when chloride-induced corrosion occurs, local acidification occurs at the corrosion pit. Therefore, the performance of corrosion inhibitors in low-pH environments must be studied. In a chloride-induced corrosion process, reinforcing steel bars have been exposed to solutions that simulate the electrolytic environment of concrete micropores during the corrosion propagation period. Sodium nitrate (NaNO₃) has been added to these solutions to study their performance as corrosion inhibitors. Solutions consisted of saturated calcium hydroxide (Ca [OH]₂) with the progressive addition of iron (II) chloride (FeCl₂) to obtain different pH values in the basic zone. NaCl₂ was used for neutral solutions, and different concentrations of FeCl₂ for acid solutions. Steel corrosion rates were measured using the polarization resistance technique. The results of the electrochemical impedance spectroscopy are also presented to support the observations. According to the results, NaNO₃ reduces corrosion levels in basic environments and does not show significant improvement in acidic solutions. Corrosion of steel is related to the [Cl⁻]/[OH⁻] ratio in three different pH regions, ranging from acidic to basic.

Jafar et al. [30] contended that metals are used in over 90% of construction units in the chemical and petroleum industries. Iron and steel are widely used metals in the fabrication and manufacturing of petroleum field operating platforms. Exposure of metals to the effect of bases or acids in various industries can be severe to the metals' specifications, resulting in the sudden failure of materials in service. Therefore, the need to investigate the protection of metals when exposed to various environments is a critical factor in the selection of material that determines its service life. In the present study, the effect of various concentrations of sodium nitrate ranging from 25 to 100 mg/l on the corrosion inhibition of carbon steel placed in different concentrations of hydrochloric acid

solution (1, 2, and 3 M) was studied. The results showed that the sodium nitrate concentration of 75 mg/l achieved the best inhibition of the acid used in all the concentrations used, as it reduced the corrosion rate by 48.91%, 39.38%, and 35.33% for 1 M, 2 M, and 3 M, respectively.

Hilca and Triyono [31] experimentally evaluated the effect of sodium nitrate inhibitors (NaNO_3) of 0.1%, 0.3%, and 0.5% on NaCl 3.5% toward pitting corrosion of dissimilar metal welding joints between stainless steel AISI 304 and mild steel SS 400. The electrochemical corrosion was tested using potentiodynamic polarization. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was used to analyze the specimen. Chemical composition analysis was performed using energy-dispersive X-ray spectrometry (EDS). The highest efficiency of sodium nitrate was 63.8% for ER 308 and 64.89% for ER 309L. The specimen surface, which was observed through SEM, showed a decrease in pitting corrosion with the addition of sodium nitrate as an inhibitor.

Mohammed [32] contended that corrosion of steel reinforcement is one of the biggest problems facing all countries in the world, such as bridges in the beach area and marine constructions, which leads to studying these problems and applying some economical solutions. Given the high repair costs associated with these constructions, we studied the effect of using the chemical compounds sodium nitrite (NaNO_2) and sodium silicate (Na_2SiO_3) as corrosion inhibitor admixtures for steel bars that are partially immersed in an electrolyte solution (water + sodium chloride in 3% conc.) (Approximately similar to the concentration of salt in seawater). The two inhibitors above were added, each one to the electrolyte solution at concentrations of 0.5%, 1%, and 2%. The results showed that the corrosion rate for the steel sample partially immersed in a salt solution was higher than that of the steel bar partially immersed in an electrolyte solution with inhibitors. The two corrosion inhibitors (sodium nitrite and sodium silicate) that were added to the electrolyte solution successfully prevented and inhibited corrosion using the weight loss technique with the best percentage of 0.5% sodium nitrite (efficiency 94.1%) and the best percentage of 2% sodium silicate (efficiency 92.5%).

Hassan [33] used the weight loss technique to study the effect of some variables on the corrosion rate of carbon steel in a crude oil medium. The test system was designed to measure the corrosion rate. The experimental medium was crude oil. The corrosion performance of carbon steel was tested at temperatures of 20, 30, 40, 50, and 60 rpm, rotational velocities of 0, 1000, and 2000 rpm; and NaNO_3 inhibitor concentrations of 0, 0.5, and 1.1 g/l. The corrosion rate decreased with increasing inhibitor concentration in crude oil but increased with increasing rotational velocity and temperature. Temperature affected the corrosion rate by changing two main parameters, i.e., oxygen solubility and diffusivity. The best efficiency of NaNO_3 as a chemical inhibitor in crude oil was 98% at a temperature of 20°C, 1.1 g/L concentration, and 0 rpm rotational velocity. The experimental results were quantified using the non-linear curve fitting technique by Hooke-Jeeves and the quasi-Newton method, which were included in the statistical program package at different concentrations of NaNO_3 inhibitor in crude oil. The following equations have been found: For using 0.5 g/l NaNO_3 , $Sh = 1.26$, $Re = 0.025$, $Sc = 0.0087$, with a correlation coefficient C.C. = 0.89 and a mean error of 5.42%. For using 1.1 g/l NaNO_3 , $Sh = 1.04$, $Re = 0.025$, $Sc = 0.0113$, with a C.C. = 0.92 and a mean error of 2.68%.

Murmu et al. [34] contended that metallic materials undergo deterioration because of their reactions on exposure to different environments, and this is termed "corrosion." Corrosion directly or indirectly causes severe degradation of metallic materials, which sometimes remain unrenovated, ultimately leading to impending catastrophic failure, accidents, and shutdown of industries and infrastructures. All of these are associated with huge economic drainage. Thus, several techniques, such as alloying and dealloying of metallic materials, electroplating, and anodic or cathodic protection, have been developed to combat the adverse consequences associated with corrosion. Among such techniques, corrosion inhibitors and coating materials are endorsed for

several applications owing to their straightforward and easy application. Nitrates are used as inorganic anticorrosive materials (IAMs) as inorganic corrosion-inhibiting additives to protect metallic materials exposed to corrosive environments. The addition of anticorrosive ingredients to coating materials is one of the most prevalent strategies in mitigating the degradation of metallic materials due to corrosive attacks. Several compounds of nitrates, such as lithium nitrate, sodium nitrate, magnesium nitrate, aluminum nitrate, potassium nitrate, calcium nitrate, zinc nitrate, lanthanum nitrate, and cerium nitrate, are utilized, separately or in combined form, as corrosion-inhibiting materials for protecting several metallic substrates, such as copper, zinc, magnesium, mild steel, cold-rolled steel, and low-carbon steel, in different corrosive environments, such as aqueous NaCl, HCl, NaIO₄, H₃PO₄, cement mortar, and humid environments. Herein, the workability of IAMs has been reviewed from the existing literature, and the corrosion inhibition mechanism has been comprehensively discussed. Research and development in IAMs is ongoing, and nitrates may be established as preferable and efficient corrosion inhibitors for use in the near future.

Xu et al. [35] asserted that nitrate is significant for the corrosion process, which has been extensively studied for decades. However, some issues remain unclear. Adsorption and reduction mechanisms are widely proposed but separately in the literature, and results regarding different corrosion modes and conditions are inconsistent. The adsorption mechanism of nitrate, mostly as competitive adsorption against chloride, is discussed in terms of electrode potential, concentration, temperature, and alloy composition. However, it must be based on the premise that nitrate cannot stimulate corrosion, which cannot be fully interpreted by the adsorption mechanism. The nitrate reduction mechanism, which consumes protons and produces water to lower aggressiveness compensates this inadequacy. Based on these mechanisms, the effect of nitrate on the localized corrosion of carbon steel and stainless steel in aqueous solutions, including pitting, crevice corrosion, and cracking, is reviewed in detail. Nitrate tends to passivate the salt-covered pit, but not the salt-free pit, because proton migration across the salt layer is unavailable. However, they concluded that sufficient nitrate may passivate the salt-free pit through reduction alone, although further work is required. The effect of nitrate on crevice corrosion is relatively consistent and tends to inhibit dissolution against chloride. Nitrate reduction and adsorption are also important for cracking, mostly initiated from intergranular corrosion for carbon steels due to imperfect passivation, and from localized corrosion for stainless steels. Competition between localized corrosion and cracking can be used to interpret the inhibitive/non-inhibitive/promoting effect of nitrate. Corrosion products within a local site dissolving in nitrate are also discussed, which inhibit mass transport but enhance dissolution stability. Nitrate is generally classified as an inhibitor but is described as a dangerous one.

According to Kahraman et al. [36], the weather in the Arabian Gulf region constitutes an environment that is corrosive to carbon steel. The high salinity of the Gulf sea-water further aggravates atmospheric corrosion in the Gulf region. In addition, sulfur dioxide and deposits from combustion products tend to make the Gulf region's atmosphere even more corrosive. Various inhibitors that can help in the prevention of metal corrosion in aqueous environments have been reported in the literature. Sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate, sodium benzoate, sodium nitrite, and sodium nitrate were obtained, and the effectiveness of certain corrosion inhibitors on carbon steel specimens was examined in a simulated atmospheric corrosion environment containing 2% NaCl and 1% Na₂SO₄ with various inhibitor concentrations. Test specimens were prepared from locally produced RS bars. The test program showed that treatment of the steel with 10- or 100-mM sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate for one day at room temperature resulted in the best corrosion inhibition. The results also demonstrated that inhibitors, such as sodium benzoate and sodium nitrite, were similarly effective, as was sodium nitrate. Further studies are planned

to examine the inhibition performance of sodium dihydrogen orthophosphate under actual atmospheric conditions.

Shwetha et al. [37] noted that corrosion is a serious problem in many industries, and metal structures in particular are susceptible to its causative damage. Therefore, it is important to take the necessary steps to protect against corrosion. Organic chemical compounds, which are significant and naturally occurring molecules, are very effective corrosion inhibitors. According to research, chemical compounds containing oxygen, sulfur, and nitrogen have the strongest inhibitory action. Organic and natural corrosion inhibitors protect metal surfaces by forming protective films. This review focused on the effectiveness of natural corrosion inhibitors and organic compounds in preventing corrosion. The review also examined how some of these compounds halted the corrosion of mild steel in acidic solutions using electrochemical impedance and polarization. The adsorption behavior and thermodynamic variables were also examined. SEM micrographs were used to analyze the surface morphology of mild steel. In this review paper, the types of corrosion, inhibitors, control measures, and techniques for the corrosion control of mild steel are discussed. This will provide the inhibition mechanism, inhibition efficiency, and effective corrosion control method. Theoretical studies, activation parameter adsorption studies, and surface morphology were also discussed. Overall, this paper provides a glimpse of corrosion control and research gaps in this scenario. This study aims to encourage a wider use of organic corrosion inhibitors by providing a comprehensive overview of current research on this topic.

Ress et al. [38] reported that the use of nitrite- and nitrate-based inhibitors provides corrosion protection by developing a passive oxide film on the metal surface in reinforced concrete applications. However, the impact of the nitrite and nitrate ratio in the mixture has not been widely studied. In this study, the corrosion protection provided by $\text{NaNO}_2:\text{NaNO}_3$ inhibitor blends with ratios of 0.5:1, 1:1, and 1:0.5 was studied to maximize corrosion inhibition efficiency. The nitrite species imparted higher corrosion protection, as shown by cyclic potentiodynamic polarization, with an i_{corr} of $1.16 \times 10^{-7} \text{ A/cm}^2$ for the 1:0.5 mixture, which was lower than that for both the 1:1 and 0.5:1 mixture. Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was also performed, with the 1:0.5 mixture consistently displaying high resistance values, showing an R_{ct} of $1.31 \times 10^5 \text{ } \Omega \text{ cm}^2$. The effect of temperature was also assessed; the E_a values of the corrosion reaction were calculated to be 12.1, 9.2, and 4.9 kJ/mol for the 0.5:1, 1:1, and 1:0.5 ($\text{NO}_2^-:\text{NO}_3^-$) mixtures, respectively. Density functional theory was applied to analyze the molecular properties and determine the relationship between the quantum properties and corrosion inhibition. The ΔE of NO_2^- was found to be -5.74 eV , lower than that of NO_3^- (-5.45 eV), corroborating the experimental results. Finally, commercially available inhibitor mixtures were investigated and nitrite/nitrate concentrations were determined to evaluate their corrosion protection performance. Sika outperformed Yara due to its greater NO_2^- concentration.

Asadikiya and Ghorbani [39] investigated the effects of inhibitors consisting of sodium nitrite (NaNO_2), sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), sodium molybdate (Na_2MoO_4), and sodium silicate (Na_2SiO_3) on the corrosion behavior of aluminum alloy 3303 (UNS A93303) in a mixture of water and ethylene glycol ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_6\text{O}_2$). In the first part of the investigation, tests were conducted without any galvanic coupling. In the second part, galvanic connections between the aluminum alloy and mild steel, stainless steel, copper, brass, and solder were established. The results show that sodium nitrate is the best corrosion inhibitor in both situations, according to its ability to reduce the corrosion rate, passivate the aluminum surface, and stop pitting corrosion.

Gao et al. [40] noted that the corrosion resistance of Al-based amorphous alloy can be significantly improved with the addition of NaNO_3 into NaCl solution. The growth rates of the passive film in the initial immersion stage are accelerated, and metastable pitting is inhibited. The pitting potential of the Al-based amorphous alloy is

increased with the concentration of NaNO_3 , and pitting corrosion is completely avoided when the concentration of NaNO_3 is above 0.03 M. The transition from pitting to trans-passivation can be attributed to the incorporation of NO_3^- in passive film. Sodium nitrate is an effective corrosion inhibitor for Al-based amorphous alloys.

3.0 OVERALL REVIEW FINDINGS

The overall literature review findings show that acidic water environments can cause extremely dangerous corrosion of mild steel in various aqueous environments. Sodium nitrate is a highly effective corrosion inhibitor of mild steel when used in aqueous environments at sufficiently high concentrations. Its advantages for industrial applications as a corrosion inhibitor of mild steel are fast passive film formation that retards corrosion agents such as chlorides from contacting the steel surface; enhancement of the strength integrity of the steel; cost-effectiveness; pitting and other corrosion attack reduction probability; compatibility with hot water and industrial cooling water closed-loop systems; and eco-friendliness. It is also non-volatile, has minimal effects on personnel, and is environmentally stable. The review shows that its corrosion inhibition in aqueous environments is mostly focused on neutral-to-alkaline environments and oxygenated environments such as simulated cooling waters, concrete pore solution, and industrial cleaning solutions. However, its corrosion inhibition in several aqueous water environments from different locations or resources and aqueous environments at high temperatures above 70°C , sour environments, highly saline, especially chloride aqueous environments, and high flow-velocity aqueous environments have not been reconciled by research.

4.0 CONCLUSION

An up-to-date literature review on the corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic water environments with sodium nitrate has been conducted. The review shows that mild steel is the most important steel type and structural metal in terms of versatility, cost-effectiveness, wide availability, fabrication properties, etc., coupled with very high strengths. However, it is the most corrodible of all steel types and all other structural materials. Acidic water environments are among the most aggressive environments, causing extremely dangerous corrosion of mild steel by accelerating its corrosion rate to failure with the possibility of unpredictable hazardous consequences in structural applications. Sodium nitrate is one of the inhibitors studied and used for the corrosion inhibition of mild steel in acidic water environments. When used at sufficiently high concentrations, usually above 500 ppm in water environments, it highly inhibits mild steel corrosion. Its benefits as a corrosion inhibitor for mild steel include the ability to quickly create a protective layer to keep corrosive substances such as chlorides away from the steel surface, maintaining the strength integrity of the steel, its affordability, its high chance of reducing pitting and other corrosion types, its ability to work well in closed-loop systems such as hot water loops and industrial cooling waters, and being safe for industrial environments. It is also non-volatile, generally has minimal effect on personnel, and is environmentally stable. Its corrosion inhibition of the steel in several aqueous water environments from different locations or resources and aqueous environments at high temperatures above 70°C , sour environments, highly saline, especially chloride aqueous environments, and high flow-velocity aqueous environments has, however, not yet been reconciled by research.

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